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4 **Templates as shadow masks to tune the magnetic anisotropy in**
5 **nanostructured Co-Cr-Pt/Ti bilayer films**
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10 *David Navas*, Lei Bi, Adekunle O. Adeyeye and Caroline A. Ross*
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16 Dr. David Navas
17

18 Department of Materials Science and Engineering, Massachusetts Institute of Technology,
19 Cambridge, Massachusetts 02139, USA.

20 *Present address:* IFIMUP-IN and Departamento Física e Astronomia, Univ. Porto, 4169-
21 007 Porto, Portugal.
22

23
24 E-mail: davidnavasotero@gmail.com
25
26

27
28 Dr. Lei Bi
29

30 Department of Materials Science and Engineering, Massachusetts Institute of Technology,
31 Cambridge, Massachusetts 02139, USA.

32 *Present address:* School of Microelectronics and Solid State Electronics, University of
33 Electronic Science and Engineering of China, Chengdu, Sichuan, P.R. China 610054.
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36

37
38 Prof. Adekunle O. Adeyeye
39

40 Department of Electrical and Computer Engineering, National University of Singapore,
41 117576, Singapore.
42
43
44

45
46 Prof. Caroline A. Ross
47

48 Department of Materials Science and Engineering, Massachusetts Institute of Technology,
49 Cambridge, Massachusetts 02139, USA.
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58 thickness-dependent nanostructures
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Abstract

Off-axis deposition of Ti and CoCrPt films onto lithographically patterned templates has been used to make nanostructures with a lateral thickness variation which allows the tuning of the magnetic anisotropy. CoCrPt rectangles of $1\ \mu\text{m} \times 725\ \text{nm}$ without a thickness variation showed an out-of-plane easy axis and a single domain configuration after demagnetization. On the other hand, rectangles with a thickness variation along their longer dimension showed an out-of-plane multidomain state, but an in-plane vortex configuration occurred when the thickness variation is along the shorter dimension. The evolution of the magnetic behaviour is understood from the change in both Ti and CoCrPt thickness and their effects on the magnetic anisotropy, and provides a simple method for controlling the magnetic state and reversal process of patterned nanostructures.

1. Introduction

Magnetic nanostructures are essential components of emerging technologies such as spintronics,^[1,2] magnetic random access memory,^[3] magnetostatically coupled logic devices^[4] and magnetic field sensors.^[5] In particular, ferromagnetic materials with out-of-plane magnetic anisotropy have been widely studied for perpendicular magnetic recording media^[6,7] as well as for patterned magnetic media.^[8,9]

The rapid improvement in fabrication of nanostructured systems has been based on the development of lithographic techniques, both conventional and those based on self-assembly.^[10] Deposition and liftoff is commonly used for the fabrication of micro- and nanostructures, but shadowing effects originated by the template reduce film uniformity or even generate discontinuities.^[11] These shadowing effects can be useful, for example in the fabrication of metal electrodes separated by sub-10 nm gaps.^[12] More recently, shadowing combined with off-normal or glancing angle deposition (GLAD) has provided a range of morphologies by exploiting atomic shadowing effects during physical vapor deposition on planar substrates.^[13-15] A variety of nanostructures, such as magnetic nanowire arrays,^[16] periodically structured columnar thin films,^[17] magnetic multilayers for perpendicular giant magnetoresistance devices,^[18] arrays of closed and open loop-shaped nanostructures for

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4 optical applications,^[19] plasmonic nanoparticle arrays with nanometer separation for surface
5 enhanced Raman spectroscopy (SERS) substrates,^[20] C-shaped nanostructures for
6 metamaterial architectures, plasmonic biosensors and optical antennas^[21,22] and concentric
7 rings and disks for sensors with multiple chemical active regions^[23] have been reported
8 when deposition was combined with shadowing effects originating from a template or the
9 substrate topography, such as V-groove patterned substrates. Most deposition is carried out
10 with flux normal to the substrate plane, but isolated Fe particle arrays,^[24] Ni nanorings,^[25]
11 Co and Co/Pt multilayer particle arrays,^[26] and NiFe cylindrical nanoshells, nanocups and
12 perforated nanocups^[27] are ferromagnetic systems which have been recently studied using
13 template shadow effects and GLAD or off-axis deposition.
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16 Moreover, there has been a growing interest in periodic nanostructures made from
17 two different materials or bi-component systems because they can be used as magnonic
18 crystals^[28,29] and for magnetic recording application such as tilted media,^[30,31] lateral
19 exchange spring media^[32,33] and vertically graded anisotropy media.^[34,35] However, the
20 fabrication of these structures usually requires several lithographic and pattern transfer
21 steps. In order to simplify these processes, GLAD in combination with template shadow
22 effects has been shown as an alternative for the fabrication of structures made from two
23 different materials, such as bi-component NiFe/Fe or Ni/NiFe nanostructures^[36,37] or
24 thickness-modulated NiFe disks.^[38]
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27 These results illustrate the versatility of off-axis deposition for making a wide range
28 of sample geometries, but this technique can also be used to produce nanostructures with
29 properties that vary near the edges of the structure. In this article, we use off-normal
30 shadow deposition to obtain nanostructures with a lateral thickness distribution and a
31 gradient in magnetic anisotropy along a specific direction. The films in this study were
32 nominally Ti (3 nm)/Co_{0.66}Cr_{0.22}Pt_{0.12} (20 nm)/Ti (5 nm). The ferromagnetic CoCrPt alloy,
33 has an uniaxial magnetocrystalline anisotropy with easy axis along the c-axis.^[39] Depending
34 on the underlayer, the c-axis orientation can be randomly distributed, giving an in-plane
35 magnetization dominated by shape anisotropy, or out-of-plane oriented by epitaxial growth
36 onto an underlayer such as Ti (0001).^[40,41] Moreover, the anisotropy energy of CoCrPt
37 films with an out-of-plane c-axis depends on the layer thickness, being smaller for thinner
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4 films.^[42-44] In this study thickness gradients caused by off-axis deposition led to gradients
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6 in thickness and magnetic properties across the nanostructures.

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8 Although we focused on the fabrication of magnetic materials, this simple process
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10 can produce tapered structures with gradients in a range of properties, with applications in
11 electronics,^[12] optics,^[19] surface enhanced Raman spectroscopy (SERS),^[20] chemical
12 sensors^[23] and new and emerging research fields like nano-plasmonic biosensors, optical
13 antennas^[21,22] and magnonics,^[28,29,36-38] where the engineering of spatially varying
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15 properties is required.
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20 21 **2. Results and Discussion**

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24 Patterned rectangles of CoCrPt were made over a silicon substrate with a native
25 oxide using deep ultra-violet lithography, sputter-deposition, and lift-off techniques. The
26 sputtering gun was tilted to angle $\alpha \approx 84^\circ$ with respect to the film plane. In order to study
27 the effect of the template as a shadow mask, samples were deposited with and without
28 sample rotation (30 rpm). For comparison, 20 nm thick CoCrPt unpatterned films were also
29 deposited with and without rotation. The rotation of the sample resulted in nanostructures
30 with a small edge taper whereas static deposition generated sample with a side to side
31 thickness gradient.
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40 41 **2.1. Unpatterned films**

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44 First of all, and as a control, the effect of sample rotation on unpatterned films
45 deposited onto a flat Si substrate was explored. **Figure 1(a)** shows one-dimensional XRD
46 patterns of the 20 nm thick CoCrPt films when the layers were grown with and without
47 rotation. Si (200) and CoCrPt (0002) peaks appeared almost identical XRD with the (0002)
48 CoCrPt peaks at $2\theta = 43.74^\circ$ and 43.75° for rotated and static samples respectively,
49 indicating a polycrystalline film with (0001) texture. The (0002) CoCrPt peak was
50 measured by two-dimensional XRD where the detection was ranged from -15° to $+15^\circ$ for
51 both the chi and the 2θ axes. Figures 1(b) and (c) were obtained at an X-ray incident angle
52 of $\theta = 21.8^\circ$ and frame center of $2\theta = 43.6^\circ$. There was a larger spread in the chi direction
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4 ($\pm 7^\circ$) for the (0002) peak of the sample with rotation (figure 1(b)) compared with the static
5 sample (figure 1(c)) which showed a spread of $\pm 4.5^\circ$.
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8 The hysteresis loops of Ti/20 nm CoCrPt/Ti films with and without rotation
9 confirmed the expected out-of-plane easy magnetization direction (figure 1(d)) due to the
10 crystallographic c-axis orientation perpendicular to the sample plane. The out-of-plane
11 hysteresis loops had a remanence ratio ≈ 1 . The film grown with rotation had depinning and
12 coercive fields of 65 and 139 Oe, respectively, while the static sample showed smaller
13 values of 13 and 128 Oe. The in-plane loops were characteristic of a hard axis, with only a
14 small low field step. From the hysteresis loops, the uniaxial out-plane anisotropy energy K_u
15 = $(1.23 \pm 0.01) \times 10^6$ ergs/cm³ and $M_S = (350 \pm 10)$ emu/cm³, in agreement with literature
16 values,^[39] were estimated for both samples.
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20 MFM images of ac-demagnetized 20 nm thick CoCrPt films, with and without
21 rotation, are shown in figures 1(f) and (g). A maze domain structure, typical of thin films
22 with out-of-plane anisotropy, was found in both cases. From the self-correlation transform
23 of the MFM images,^[45] estimations of the average domain size were (180 ± 10) nm and
24 (150 ± 10) nm for the rotated and static samples, respectively. While the domains are
25 randomly distributed in the rotated film (figure 1(f)), the static sample (figure 1(g)) shows
26 that they are slightly oriented. This fact could reflect a small in-plane anisotropy in the
27 static CoCrPt thin film. However, no significant differences were observed in the in-plane
28 hysteresis loops of the static film when the magnetic field was applied along and
29 perpendicular to the direction of the deposition flux angle (figure 1(e)). Therefore the
30 existence of significant in-plane anisotropy has been dismissed.
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34 In summary, a small difference in the dispersion of the crystallographic c-axis
35 perpendicular to the sample plane, $\approx 2.5^\circ$, and in the average domain sizes were determined
36 between the films growth with and without rotation, but this did not lead to large
37 differences in the hysteresis loops or MFM images of unpatterned films.
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67 The morphology of CoCrPt rectangle arrays fabricated with an incident deposition
68 angle of $\alpha = 84^\circ$ (see diagram in **figures 2(a)** and (b)) is shown in the SEM images, figures

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4 2(c) and (d). The rectangles had long and short axis lengths of 1 μm and 725 nm,
5 respectively, and samples were made with an inter-element spacing of 65 nm (figure 2(c))
6 or 300 nm (figure 2(d)).
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10 As the sputter flux is off-normal, a lateral thickness dependence is caused by the
11 resist pattern acting as a shadow mask. This was quantified by AFM images from which 3D
12 and top-view color map surfaces of typical CoCrPt rectangles were extracted (**figure 3**).
13 When the sample was rotated during the sputtering process, patterns with symmetrical
14 thickness distribution were obtained with an edge taper (figure 3(a)). A thickness gradient
15 was noticeable when the samples were statically deposited. Two kinds of samples were
16 fabricated: with the incident flux along the longer (Long-Axis Sample in figure 3(b)) or the
17 shorter (Short-Axis Sample in figure 3(c)) rectangle axis, indicated by a black arrow in
18 figures 3(b) and (c). In the Long-Axis Sample (figure 3(b)), the thickness increased along
19 the long axis of the rectangle and it reached a maximum value of 24.8–28 nm (red in the
20 color scale) over more than 50% of the area. However, significantly more area is covered
21 by the taper in the Short-Axis Sample.
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32 In-plane and out-of-plane hysteresis loops of rectangle arrays, separated by 65 nm,
33 with (**figure 4(a)**) and without rotation (figures 4(b) and (c)) were measured. In the in-plane
34 hysteresis loops, the external magnetic field was always applied along the long axis of the
35 rectangles. The rotated sample showed a perpendicular easy magnetization axis (figure
36 4(a)) with a coercivity of 739 Oe, higher than the unpatterned film, and the reduced
37 remanence was 0.52, with a small step at low field. There was a clear hysteresis in the in-
38 plane loop.
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44 In the Long-Axis Sample (figure 4(b)), the rectangle array also shows a
45 perpendicular easy magnetization axis, with a coercivity of 248 Oe, and a reduced
46 remanence of 0.6. The in-plane loop, applying the magnetic field along the rectangles long
47 axis, also showed a significant hysteresis. However, the Short-Axis Sample (figure 4(c))
48 exhibited an unexpected behaviour in which the easy magnetization axis lies in-plane and
49 the shape of the in-plane loop suggests that the rectangles are magnetized in-plane with a
50 vortex configuration, with low remanence and an out-of-plane hard axis.
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57 MFM images, obtained after out-of-plane AC demagnetization, confirm an out-of-
58 plane domain structure for the rotated array with symmetrical thickness distribution, where
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4 each rectangle behaved as an out-of-plane single domain (figure 4(d)). The rotated sample
5 therefore consists of rectangles with primarily out-of-plane magnetization but with a thin
6 border of in-plane magnetized material. The Long-Axis Sample (figure 4(e)) showed an
7 out-of-plane multidomain structure, and the Short-Axis Sample showed an in-plane vortex
8 configuration (figures 4(f) and (g)).
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13 The increase in the area fraction of CoCrPt with an in-plane easy axis in the
14 shadowed samples is attributed to a decrease in the Ti underlayer thickness and the CoCrPt
15 thickness. Ti < 3 nm is ineffective at producing an out-of-plane c-axis, and the CoCrPt
16 layer instead shows little or no texture and an in-plane magnetization. Assuming that the Ti
17 and CoCrPt film thicknesses scale proportionately in the shadowed areas, in the Ti (5 nm,
18 underlayer)/CoCrPt (20nm)/Ti (3 nm, capping layer) stack, a total thickness larger than
19 16.8 nm would be required to obtain a 3 nm thick Ti seedlayer and a CoCrPt-alloy with
20 perpendicular magnetization axis. Therefore, the thickness distribution shown in Figure 3
21 produces an area (from dark blue to green in the color scale bar of the surface map contour)
22 where in-plane easy magnetization axis is expected.
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31 3D simulations^[46] of the statically deposited samples were performed using 2D
32 periodic boundary conditions^[47] assuming a 65 nm inter-element spacing and after out-of-
33 plane demagnetization. As the CoCrPt films consist of polycrystalline grains, the
34 microstructure was modeled using grains^[48] with volumes of $(10 \times 10 \times 20) \text{ nm}^3$ in which
35 each grain had a random 7° deviation of its uniaxial anisotropy from the film normal, based
36 on the x-ray diffraction measurements of the distribution of the crystallographic c-axis.^[49]
37 The cell size was set to $(5 \times 5 \times 5) \text{ nm}^3$, saturation magnetization M_S was taken as 350
38 emu/cm³, in agreement with literature values,^[39] and the exchange stiffness constant was A
39 $= 5 \times 10^{-7} \text{ ergs/cm}$.^[50]
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48 The modeled rectangles were extracted from the AFM images, shown in figure 3,
49 and they were divided into 4 thickness regions (**figures 5(a) and (b)**). While regions I
50 (black) and II (green) had a CoCrPt thickness of 5 and 10 nm, respectively, regions III
51 (yellow) and IV (blue) were 15 and 20 nm thick. Moreover, the Ti seed layer was thinner
52 than 3 nm for regions I and II, and thicker than 3 nm for regions III and IV. This suggests
53 that regions I and II would have an in-plane magnetization, and III and IV a perpendicular
54 magnetization. From the hysteresis loops of the continuous thin films, a uniaxial out-of-
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4 plane anisotropy energy of $K_u = (1.23 \pm 0.01) \times 10^6$ ergs/cm³ was estimated. However, we
5 should note that the effective anisotropy energy of perpendicular CoCrPt films is smaller
6 for thinner films^[42-44] and is further reduced when they are patterned.^[43] Therefore the best
7 results were obtained when the magnetocrystalline anisotropy energy was taken as $K_u^I = 0$
8 ergs/cm³, $K_u^{II} = 0$ ergs/cm³, $K_u^{III} = 0.65 \times 10^6$ ergs/cm³, and $K_u^{IV} = 0.85 \times 10^6$ ergs/cm³, for
9 regions I, II, III and IV, respectively.
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15 The model predicted an out-of-plane multidomain structure for the Long-Axis
16 Sample (figure 5(c)) with the magnetization showing more in-plane component in the
17 thinner region. The Short-Axis Sample (figure 5(d)) showed an in-plane vortex
18 configuration which was distorted at the location of the thickest part of the rectangle. These
19 results are in good agreement with the observed behavior, even though the model neglected
20 several aspects such as finite temperature effects and assumed periodic boundary
21 conditions.
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27 To clarify the role of inter-element magnetostatic interactions, weakly-interacting
28 rectangle arrays with and without rotation were also made with interelement distances of
29 300 nm. As an example, both hysteresis loops and MFM images show out-of-plane single
30 domain structure for a rectangle array made with rotation (**figures 6(a) and (b)**) and an in-
31 plane vortex configuration for a statically deposited rectangle array (figures 6(c) and (d))
32 with 300 nm separation. Weak contrast at the edges of the rotated array is attributed to the
33 in-plane magnetized regions. Therefore, we can dismiss the argument that the magnetic
34 behavior of the nanostructures could be associated with magnetostatic interactions and
35 confirm that the thickness gradient controlled the effective anisotropy of the nanostructures.
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45 46 **3. Summary** 47

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50 In an off-axis shadow-deposition process, by controlling certain parameters,
51 specifically the template thickness, the amount of deposited material, substrate rotation and
52 the deposition angle (or even changing this angle during the deposition process),
53 nanostructures with a wide range of thickness distributions and effective anisotropies can
54 be fabricated. In the CoCrPt/Ti rectangles studied here, the magnetic configuration was
55 changed between single domain perpendicular magnetization, multidomain perpendicular
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4 magnetization, and in plane magnetization vortex state by changing the rotation and
5 incident flux direction. Related effects may be expected in any thin film system whose
6 magnetic properties depend on the thickness of the magnetic layer or of its seed or capping
7 layers. Furthermore, this process provides a simple and cost-effective method to prepare
8 nanostructures for applications in multiple fields such as patterned media, magnonics,
9 nano-optics, and plasmonics by tuning those properties which show thickness-dependent
10 behaviour such as bulk and surface magnetic anisotropy energies, strength and frequency of
11 plasmon resonances, or the electrical properties of conductive films.
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21 **4. Experimental methods**

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24 Patterned rectangles of CoCrPt were made over a large area (4x4 mm²) of silicon
25 substrate with a native oxide using deep ultra-violet lithography, sputter-deposition, and
26 lift-off techniques. The patterns were prepared by deep ultra-violet lithography technique at
27 248 nm wavelength^[51] to produce a resist pattern of ≈ 200 nm thickness. A 5 nm Ti seed
28 layer, a 20 nm thick Co 66 at. %/Cr 22 at. %/Pt 12 at. % film and 3 nm Ti capping layer
29 were deposited sequentially by rf-sputtering at room temperature^[43] with a base pressure
30 below 2×10^{-8} Torr. The Ar (99.999% pure) sputtering gas pressure was 2×10^{-4} Torr and
31 the rf-power was 300 W for 5-cm-diameter targets. The deposition rates were 0.8 Å/s for Ti
32 and 1.9 Å/s for CoCrPt. The sputtering gun was tilted to angle $\alpha \approx 84^\circ$ with respect to the
33 film plane and samples were deposited with and without sample rotation (30 rpm). The lift-
34 off procedure was carried out by submerging the samples in N-methyl-2-pyrrolidone at
35 135°C in an ultrasonic bath. For comparison, 20 nm thick CoCrPt unpatterned films were
36 also deposited with and without rotation.
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48 Characterization was performed by high-resolution scanning electron microscopy
49 (HRSEM) in a JEOL 6320FV. The crystal structure of the films were examined by X-ray
50 diffraction (1D XRD) using Cu K α radiation, $\lambda = 0.15406$ nm (RIGAKU, D/MAX-2500).
51 Two-dimensional X-ray diffraction methods (2D XRD, Bruker D8 with General Area
52 Detector Diffraction System) were also used to detect the spatial distribution of the
53 diffraction peaks by rotating the sample by 360° around the axis normal to the sample
54 surface for a fixed θ -2 θ alignment.
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4 Room temperature magnetic hysteresis loops were measured in a Vibrating Sample
5 Magnetometer (VSM, ADE model 1660). Atomic and Magnetic Force Microscopy images
6 (AFM and MFM) were obtained in a Veeco/Digital Instruments Nanoscope IIIa with low-
7 moment Veeco tips. Images were obtained after an out-of-plane ac demagnetizing process
8 in which the sample was first saturated with an out-of-plane field of +10 kOe, then
9 alternating positive and negative out-of-plane fields were applied where the field at each
10 step was -0.9 times that of the previous step.

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17 Finally, micromagnetic simulations were performed using the National Institute of
18 Standards and Technology (NIST) object-oriented micromagnetic framework (OOMMF)
19 code.^[46] The cell sizes and materials parameters are described below, and the damping
20 parameter was taken as 0.5 so that the model would converge quickly.
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25 26 **Acknowledgments**

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Figure 1. (a) 1D-XRD patterns of rotated (\square) and static (---) 20 nm thick CoCrPt films. 2D-XRD patterns of rotated (b) and static (c) 20 nm thick CoCrPt films. (d) Hysteresis loops of rotated (\blacksquare and \triangle) and static (\circ and ---) 20 nm thick CoCrPt films when the magnetic field was applied out-of-plane (\blacksquare and \circ) and in-plane (\triangle and ---). (e) In-plane hysteresis loops of the static 20 nm thick CoCrPt film when the external magnetic field was applied along (\square) and perpendicular (---) to the deposition flux angle. MFM images of rotated (f) and static (g) 20 nm thick CoCrPt films after an out-of-plane AC demagnetization process.

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Figure 2. Diagram of fabrication method and thickness distribution of the film when the samples are deposited at an incident angle ($\alpha = 84^\circ$) with rotation (a) and without rotation or static configuration (b). SEM images of 20 nm thick CoCrPt rectangle with inter-element spacing of 65 (c) and 300 nm (d). Note that the diagrams in figures 1 (a) and (b) are not to scale.

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Figure 3. 3D, top-view color map surfaces and profiles of 20 nm thick CoCrPt rectangles with (a) and without rotation, Long-Axis Sample (b) and Short-Axis Sample (c), obtained from the AFM images. The same height scale or color bar scale is used for all cases.

Figure 4. Hysteresis loops of CoCrPt rectangle arrays with (a) and without (b and c) rotation when the magnetic field was applied out-of-plane (■) and in-plane along the rectangles long axis (—). Hysteresis loops of Long-Axis Sample and Short-Axis Sample are shown in (b) and (c), respectively. AFM and MFM images, obtained after out-of-plane AC demagnetization, of CoCrPt rectangle arrays deposited with rotation (d), and Long-Axis Sample (e) and Short-Axis Sample (f) without rotation. (g) Magnification of the Short-Axis Sample MFM image where the rectangles, obtained from AFM images, are outlined.

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Figure 5. Diagrams of the modeled rectangles with 4 regions for the Long-Axis Sample (a) and the Short-Axis Sample (b). Top views of the micromagnetic simulations at 2.5 nm height of the Long-Axis Sample (c) and the Short-Axis Sample (d) after out-of-plane demagnetization. Red color shows the magnetic moment along the $+z$ -axis in (c) and $+x$ -axis in (d), and blue shows the magnetic moment along $-z$ -axis in (a) and $-x$ -axis in (d).

Figure 6. Hysteresis loops of the rotated (a) and static Short-Axis Sample (c) of CoCrPt rectangle arrays, separated by 300 nm, when the magnetic field was applied out-of-plane (■) and in-plane (—). MFM images, obtained after out-of-plane AC demagnetization process, of 20 nm thick CoCrPt rectangle arrays separated by 300 nm with (b) and without (d) rotation at different magnifications.